

Issue:

On the teaching of Language and Literature: reflections on epistemicide

Revista Letras Raras (RLR) journal starts its series of publications for the year of 2023 with renewed hopes. After Covid-19 pandemic is almost defeated, new expectations point us towards an effectively democratic horizon and more consequential educational policies, with greater investment in education, among other possibilities and reasons to use the verb "to hope". Thus, we begin this year with an indispensable discussion for those who recognise the importance of an education that values the Global South. Historically, we have seen the hegemony of models conceived in the Northern Hemisphere and, in this edition of RLR, the focus on teaching that turns towards the construction of new epistemes is highlighted; that is, teaching that seeks for southing the knowledge about Language, Linguistics, and Literature.

The volume is organised by the PhD professors Maria Angélica de Oliveira and Josilene Pinheiro-Mariz, both from the Federal University of Campina Grande (UFCG), Vima Lia de Rossi Martin, from the University of São Paulo (USP), and Karolina Válková, from the Charles University Prague (Czech Republic). Initially, the issue presents the paper ***TRANSLanguaging: a decolonial perspective for language teaching***, by Themis Rondão Barbosa da Costa Silva, a PhD candidate at the State University of Campinas (UNICAMP). Its aim is to briefly present the founding principles of translanguaging, the creation of meanings from a translingual perspective, and the implications of translingual experiences in the processes of language teaching and learning from a decolonial perspective.

Following that, the paper ***Africanicide? Une problématisation de l'enseignement de variétés des français africains dans les cours de FLE à Goiânia*** [*Africanicide? A problematisation on the teaching of African French varieties in FFL courses in Goiânia*] is authored by Samuel Rufino de Carvalho, a PhD candidate at the Federal University of Paraíba (UFPB), Iury Aragonéz, a Master's student at the Federal University of Goiás (UFG), and Alexandra Almeida de Oliveira, a PhD professor at UFG. The text brings an interesting discussion on the teaching of the French language in the Brazilian context that enriches the theme addressed in this issue. The authors argue about the existence of an "africanicide", meaning the erasure of Africanities in the French as a Foreign Language (FFL) courses. The reasons mentioned include the sociocultural context, economic issues, and technical support. The authors present conclusions that point out that the teachers are not to blame; they are, so to speak, the resistance against an educational structure regulated by neocolonial violence that invades methods, institutions, artistic productions, languages, and ways of teaching French.

Afterwards, it is possible to read the paper by PhD Eduardo Oliveira Henriques de Araújo, from the Federal University of Pernambuco (UFPE). ***Epistemological colonialities: Eurocentric teaching of Portuguese language in mixed-race schools*** reflects on power relations in the ethnic-racial syntax of the Portuguese language, resulting in the relativisation of values that engender the status quo of cultural matrices that embody teaching practices in teacher education programs and, consequently, in elementary schools throughout the country.

In the sequence, the paper entitled ***Sur l'épistémicide dans les manuels de linguistique produits après la Loi Fédérale 11.645/08: Une proposition de lecture discursive*** [On epistemicide in linguistic textbooks produced after Federal Law 11.645/08: A proposal for a discursive reading] is authored by Vitória Paloma Aguiar Alves, an undergraduate student, and Maria Angélica de Oliveira, a PhD professor at UFCG. The text presents a cutting-edge discussion developed within a scientific initiation project entitled "Does the blue eye of letters see the language of non-whites?". It proposes a discursive reading of linguistic textbooks produced after Federal Law 11.645/08, which evaluates the presence (or lack thereof) of black and indigenous knowledge in four linguistics textbooks commonly used in language teaching. The authors highlight that the results demonstrate linguistic discourses of non-white peoples as undergoing a significant epistemicide, in which specific voices are silenced.

In the same vein, professor Janayara Araújo Lima and professor Roseli Bodnar, both from the Federal University of Tocantins (UFT), present ***Black women's memories: an inventory of the domestic world and things, in Conceição Evaristo's insubmissible tears of women***. The paper reveals the results of an investigation into the theme of memory as an important guiding thread for the construction of narratives in Conceição Evaristo's book. According to them, it is through the use of memories that the plots portray stories of black women affected by their social, ethnic, cultural, and gender conditions. Throughout the analysis, they relate memory to the personal condition of the rememberer, pointing out the subjective aspects that manifest themselves in the characters' memory cuts.

Moreover, the paper ***The "Poetic Of Residues" of Carolina Maria De Jesus in the Unedited Diaries***, by PhD candidate Aurielle Gomes (UFCG) and PhD professor Sinara de Oliveira Branco (UFCG), focuses on a Brazilian writer. The authors discuss the paradoxical nature of Carolina's writing, reiterating how her literary discourse represents a complex challenge for the field of translation. In order to reflect on this process, they discuss the translation into English of the last part released of the author's diaries.

In the section of non-thematic texts — completely connected to the scope of *Revista Letras Raras* journal —, professor Ionara Satin, from the State University of São Paulo (UNESP, Araraquara), presents the paper

Between the concrete and the invisible: the space of the house in the narrative of Natalia Ginzburg, seeking to analyse the house as the most evident symbol in the texts of the Italian writer Natalia Ginzburg. Throughout the text, the researcher analyses the narrative and thematic space of the house in three novels: *La strada che va in città*, *Lessico Familiare*, and *La città e la casa*. The professor's will is to understand the importance of this space in the construction of the author's fiction and to what extent the way she presents the house can show/hide the depth of her discourse.

Axiologies in dialogic comic strip reading activities is the following paper, authored by Master's candidate Flavia Gumieiro Vieira, PhD professor Cristiane Malinoski Pianaro Angelo, from the State University of Central-West (UNICENTRO), and PhD professor Adriana Delmira Mendes-Polato, from the State University of Paraná (UNESPAR). The authors aim to understand how axiological concepts of language — the extraverbal of enunciation, intonation, and value judgments — contribute to the production of meaning in the reading of a statement modulated in the comic strip genre, in order to expand readers' socio-ideological awareness.

The last paper in the issue is presented by João Gabriel Carvalho Marcelino, a PhD candidate at the Federal University of Santa Catarina (UFSC). In ***Exploring a Portuguese-English corpus through LancsBox®: possibilities for research in translation studies***, the author highlights the field of translation and uses the language processing tool LancsBox®, in order to emphasise the main aims of the study, namely: discussing the use of language processing applications and tools through Corpus Linguistics and Computational Linguistics, as well as suggesting possibilities for LancsBox® application in translation research.

Within the scope of the journal and the issue, we also read the essay ***Principles for building an ethnic and racial curriculum in the teaching of Portuguese language and literature***, by Beatriz Farias Almeida (UFMG), Francielle Loiola Ramos (UFMG), and PhD professor Denise Lino Araújo (UFMG). The text brings a fundamental discussion to think about the topic under debate. The authors seek to "construct spaces of enunciation, select linguistic aspects that allow the study of language with a view to respecting and valuing ethnic-racial relations, establish generative themes, and choose representative materials."

In ***From Epistemicide in the Letters to anti-racist education experiences: an interview with Professors Maria Angélica Oliveira and Patrícia Silva Rosas***, Amanda Lopes Bezerra (UFMG), an undergraduate student in Language and Literature, and Denise Lino De Araújo (UFMG), present us an interview with two scholars. The authors discuss the ethnic-racial relations present in the classroom, the presence of racism in the school process, and the paths that can be followed to make Brazilian education more equitable for all students.

Nevertheless, we also have within the scope of the journal some artistic creation or literary creation texts with short stories, poems, and prose poems, such as the intriguing ***Meu Coração Vive De Imaginação, Rompe Tectônicas Placas***, by Marcelo Calderari Miguel. Meanwhile, through the path of silence and pain, Maurício Fontana Filho, from the University of Passo Fundo (UPF), publishes the text ***Instinto***. Yvisson Gomes dos Santos, a PhD from the Federal University of Alagoas (UFAL), presents ***Prefácio*** — a set of poems, narratives, prose poems. To end this issue, the poem ***O salvador*** is presented by Karina Dias da Silva, a Master's candidate at La Salle University (UNILASALLE), which offers a breath of hope and inspiration in face of so many challenges and possible despair.

Dear reader of these scientific and literary texts, in this first edition of 2023, the editorial board and the organisers of this issue focus on such a necessary theme for our field, as it directly touches on the teaching of language and literature, reflecting on the historical process of the epistemicide in Language and Literature Studies. This edition brings a meaningful contribution to teachers, professors, scholars, researchers, and students in the broad area of Language and Literature Studies, so that we can build new epistemes, southing new and other narratives, providing space to a truly decolonial education. In this first issue of the year, it is also possible to access the QR Code of ***Revista Letras Raras*** journal and share the texts, in order to instigate reflections in the most varied areas of our domain, based on the contributions presented in *On the teaching of Language and Literature: reflections on epistemicide*. Therefore, the series of publications of 2023 begins with the expectation of new conjugations of the verb "to hope".

Have a nice reading for you all!

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Translated by Rafael de Arruda Sobral